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The Fabrication of Polylactic acid (PLA) / Cellulose nanofiber (CNF) Nanocomposites with Plasticizer as Dispersing Agent

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Introduction

Recent issues

- Existing food packaging materials

[뉴스+] 재활용 폐기물 대란...비닐 이어 플라스틱 확산 하나

넘치는 재활용 폐기물... 수거비가 더 들어 / 수송 길 막히자 폐지도 난색 표명 / 주민들 혼란... 화성·용인선 향의 사태업체, 페플라스틱까지 수거 거부 조짐 / 택배 증가 등 포장재 사용 늘어...“공공부문부터 감축 앞장서야”

Plastic-based waste disputed in Korea

Solid fuel made from Non-recyclable plastic

The amount of plastic waste generated in Korea (day)

Multilayer film of various materials
→ Non-recyclable

Development of Flexible Biodegradable Polymer Composites

Research objectives

1. Development of biodegradable polymer composites with excellent oxygen barrier property.
2. Development of flexible film that can be used for packaging industry by melt processing.

Uni-material → Recyclable

Experimental Design

Materials & Experimental scheme

Poly(lactide acid) (PLA)

- Grade : Ingeo Biopolymer 2003D, NatureWorks (USA)
- Melt flow index : 6.0 g/10min, 210 °C, 2.16kg (ASTM D1238)

Cellulose Nanofiber (CNF)

- Density : 1.5 g/cm³, dry powder
- Fiber dimensions : nominal fiber width of 50 nm lengths of up to several hundred microns

Triethyl citrate (TEC)

- Grade : 27500, Sigma Aldrich (USA)
- Density : 1.14 g/mL at 25 °C
- Boiling point : 235 °C / 150 mmHg

Decrease of tensile strength 50.7 %
Increase of elongation at break 3470%

Selection of TEC content considering mechanical properties

Sample preparation

1. PLA/CNF Nanocomposites (f-PLA/CNF)

2. PLA/Ethanol-CNF suspension Nanocomposites (e-PLA/CNF)

3. PLA/TEC-Ethanol-CNF suspension Nanocomposites (t-PLA/CNF)

◆ Morphological Properties (SEM)

◆ Optical Properties (3D laser microscopy)

✓ In the case of the f-PLA/CNF composite sample, **agglomeration** of CNF was found in PLA matrix, However, sample of t-PLA/CNF in which CNF was dispersed through a plasticizer observed that CNF was formed as a **network** in the PLA matrix.

◆ Rheological Properties (Rotational rheometer)

◆ Mechanical Properties (UTM)

Sample Code	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
Neat PLA	71.82 ± 0.96	9.50 ± 0.90	1.09 ± 0.11
f-CNF/PLA 0.25	74.66 ± 1.28	7.63 ± 0.79	1.29 ± 0.08
e-CNF/PLA 0.25	77.65 ± 0.49	7.95 ± 0.44	1.23 ± 0.05
f-CNF/PLA 0.5	73.31 ± 1.01	7.66 ± 0.81	1.29 ± 0.05
e-CNF/PLA 0.5	78.65 ± 0.81	8.19 ± 0.44	1.27 ± 0.06
f-CNF/PLA 1	71.44 ± 0.54	8.62 ± 1.14	1.05 ± 0.15
e-CNF/PLA 1	80.72 ± 0.54	8.80 ± 0.56	1.33 ± 0.08

Sample Code	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elongation at break (%)	Young's modulus (GPa)
t-PLA	35.75 ± 0.75	323.62 ± 37.87	0.63 ± 0.03
t-CNF/PLA 0.25	39.74 ± 0.12	339.26 ± 39.05	0.71 ± 0.04
t-CNF/PLA 0.5	42.15 ± 1.21	325.71 ± 41.07	0.89 ± 0.07
t-CNF/PLA 1	43.02 ± 1.49	308.24 ± 67.16	1.06 ± 0.09

- ✓ A plateau phenomenon was found in the low frequency range from storage modulus values of f-PLA/CNF samples containing **1 wt%** of CNF. However, in the case of t-PLA/CNF composite samples dispersed with a plasticizer, all samples with concentrations ranging from **0.25 to 1 wt%** were found to have plateau at low frequency ranges.
- ✓ This suggests the presence of a **strong CNF network** attributed to their **good dispersion** in the PLA matrix.

Results

◆ Mechanical Properties (UTM)

- ✓ Comparing plasticized PLA and P-PLA/CNF composite samples showed an **increase of tensile strength of 12.7 ~ 17.4%** depending on the content of CNF. Also, there was no significant decrease in elongation at break.
- ✓ In particular, the improved young's modulus values of t-CNF/PLA nanocomposites containing 1 wt% CNF were almost similar to that of neat PLA.
- ✓ Similar to the results of mechanical properties, it has been found that the uniform dispersion of CNF in the PLA matrix affects the improvement of oxygen barrier properties.

◆ Oxygen barrier Properties (OTR)

Sample Code	Oxygen Permeability (cc-mm/m ² -day-atm)
Neat PLA	32.26 ± 1.24
f-CNF/PLA 0.25	31.55 ± 0.08
e-CNF/PLA 0.25	32.87 ± 0.55
f-CNF/PLA 0.5	22.52 ± 0.07
e-CNF/PLA 0.5	26.43 ± 0.24
f-CNF/PLA 1	29.86 ± 0.12
e-CNF/PLA 1	15.88 ± 1.36

Sample Code	Oxygen Permeability (cc-mm/m ² -day-atm)
t-PLA	34.54 ± 2.17
t-CNF/PLA 0.25	21.23 ± 0.40
t-CNF/PLA 0.5	18.41 ± 0.07
t-CNF/PLA 1	16.99 ± 0.85

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Summary

Poly(lactic acid)
Cellulose nanofiber
Triethyl citrate

Fully
Bio-based
Materials

- i) High flexibility and improved tensile strength
- ii) Enhanced oxygen barrier property
- iii) Less migration out of plasticizer

- ✓ The reduced tensile strength due to plasticization of PLA is enhanced by the uniform dispersion of CNF, and it is expected that the uniform distribution of CNF will improve the oxygen barrier properties of the composite.
- ✓ The composites developed in this study are likely to be applied to various packaging materials.